

ON THE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGISMS

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ANNOTATION: The article discusses the role of phraseologisms in linguistics, their occurrence and use in speech, and their use in fiction. It can be used by teachers of academic lyceums and higher educational institutions in "Uzbek language" classes.

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Phraseology is the most interesting field of Uzbek linguistics. On this basis, several large-scale studies on Uzbek phraseology have been published. These studies serve as a theoretical basis for studying the phraseological richness of the language of fiction.

A phrase is a lexical unit formed based on two or more lexemes belonging to independent categories, which mainly have a nominative meaning, therefore it is placed on the same line as a lexeme, and it is considered a larger nominative unit than a lexeme.

For example, the meaning of the idiom of the phrase "to be happy" is to think, "to be happy" and the meaning of the phrase "to calm down" is similar to the meaning of the lexeme "to calm down". This language unit is called in the literature by terms such as phraseologism, and phraseological unit, and it is called phraseme, analogous to the terms lexeme and morpheme.

Phraseme is a linguistic unit, when using a phraseme equivalent to a symbol in the language memory part of the brain, this symbol is copied.

A phrase is equivalent to a part of a linguistic unit. It becomes a whole and is used in speech only after the addition of certain grammatical features. In the next case, the phrase is equal to a singular unit, it is called a phrase-form.

Variation is a phenomenon characteristic of all linguistic units, including phrases. Two- and three-option expressions are the main part of multi-variant expressions. In general, there are more variations in phrases compared to other language units, and the number of variations of one phrase reaches up to ten. Due to variation, one phrase retains the image unity and lexical meaning characteristic of another phrase.

Variantization takes place within the framework of the wholeness of the phrase itself, to the extent that this wholeness allows. Otherwise, the phrase is destroyed or a phrase is constructed. Phraseological variants are initially distinguished as lexical variants and grammatical variants. A variant created by changing a component represented by a word of an independent category in the phrase is called a lexical variant.

In this case, the word is a component: replaced, added, thrown away.

The most complicated of these is variation based on lexical substitution.

In lexical substitution, these words are mutually (1) synonyms: to'rt taraf (i) qibla – to'rt tomon (i) qibla, o'yga cho'mmoq - o'yga botmoq; (2) yaqin meaningful words are: og'ziga tolqon soldmoq – og'ziga so'k solmoq.

When synonyms are exchanged, the options differ mainly in speech and stylistic signs, thus stylistic options arise. A variant formed by grammatically changing the structure of a phrase is called a grammatical variant.

Grammatical variation, like lexical variation, mainly occurs by replacing, removing or adding a grammatical part of a sentence. There is also a unique phenomenon in grammatical variation - word-componentization.

1. Variation arising on the basis of substitution:

qo'yin(i)ini puch yong'oqqqa to'ldirmoq -

qo‘yin(i)ini puch yong‘oq bilan to‘ldirmoq
(in this case, it is replaced by an auxiliary).

2. Variant that appears on the basis of addition:

holdan toymoq –

holdan toydirmoq

(Adding a level builder plugin).

3. Variant arising on the basis of abandonment:

ko‘z(i) ilinddi – ko‘z ilindi

(based on the addition of a possessive suffix).

4. Variant arising on the basis of order change:

ko‘ngil bermoq – bergan ko‘ngil

(as a result of re-syntactic linking, the compound compound turns into a qualifying compound).

As in the case of the lexeme, two phenomena are distinguished in terms of the content of the phrase.

1. Lexical meaning, that is, phraseological meaning

2. Evaluation scheme

The lexical meaning of a phrase in relation to reality is called phraseological meaning.

Har biri otning kallasiday

In this sentence, the phrase "as big as a camel's head" means larger than usual.

The effective and appropriate use of phraseology characteristic of the universal language is often found in fiction. In this, the folk language, based on its impressive capabilities, and forms of artistic representation, creates unique individualization features of characters, ways of deviating from the norm, and great possibilities of visual means.

When he was young, he remembered that no matter how much his late

father advised him, he did not learn to pray from him and regretted it. (Odil Yakubov). In this case, the phraseology "to remember" expresses the meaning of "to remember what or who, to restore in memory".

In general, phraseologies are a language tool that, deviating from the literary norm, expresses the uniqueness of the national language, expresses the meaning more strongly, and increases the effectiveness of the characters' speech in artistic works.

List of used literature:

1. Қўчқортюв И. Бадий нутққ стилистикаси. Тошкент, 1975 йил.
2. Раҳматуллаев Ш. Ҳозиргии ўзбек адабий тили. Тошкент, 2006 йил.
3. Раҳматуллаев Ш. Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли фразеологик луғати. Тошкент, 1978 йил.
4. Раҳматуллаев Ш. Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли фразеологик луғати. Тошкент, 1978 йил.